

A STUDY OF ELECTROLYTIC OXIDATION OF CHROMIC
SULPHATE TO CHROMATE OR BICHROMATE. PART I.
POTENTIOMETRIC STUDY OF ELECTROLYTE

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The nature of the reaction at the anode causing oxidation of trivalent chromium to hexavalent form is studied potentiometrically. Potentials set up on platinum by solutions made up of various combinations of the three reactants CrO_4^{2-} , Cr^{+++} and H^+ ions are measured and the values of E_0 , obtained by using the various equations showing the mechanism of reaction, are tabulated. Those obtained by using equation,

$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} [\ln(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}) + 14\ln(\text{H}^+) - 2\ln(\text{Cr}^{+++})]$ are found to be most constant (average + 1.232 volts).

The commercial regeneration of bichromate of soda from waste bleaching liquor from pickling barrels of quaternary alloy coinage blanks having a composition: Silver 50%, Copper 40%, Nickel 5% and Zinc 5% has been worked out and the results reported in a previous paper (Mitter and Dighe, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1943, 2, 11).

During the course of that investigation, only points having direct bearing on the commercial regeneration of bichromate were investigated. The importance of understanding the fundamental chemistry and physics of the process, although realised very early, was then not pursued, as the object then was to construct a workable plant for the regeneration of bleaching liquor by passing electric current.

Certain peculiarities of the process gradually manifested themselves and it became necessary to study the chemistry of the reaction more closely to obtain an accurate insight into the fundamental changes taking place during the electrolysis.

Regelsberger (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1900, 6, 308) was the first to show that the oxidation took place with almost 100% current efficiency on lead anode but did not take place at all on platinum anode.

Le Blanc (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1901 7, 290) obtained 70-90% efficiency at 50° with lead anode. McKee and Leo published the results of their work on commercial regeneration of bichromate from waste chrome liquor (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, 12, 16). However, Müller and Soller (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1905, 11, 863) were the first to attempt to elucidate the nature of the reaction. They found that PbO_2 acted catalytically and that the electrochemical action was related to the oxidising properties of PbO_2 . The effect of additions of various compounds like KF , Na_2HPO_4 to the electrolyte was found by Schmidt (Dissertation, Charlottenberg, 1909) to be beneficial to the process of oxidation, increasing the efficiency from 82.2 to 93.9% and 98.0% respectively. The most commonly accepted mode of reaction of the electrolytic oxidation of chromium sulphate to chromic acid is represented as follows (*vide* Fajans and Wust, "Practical Physical Chemistry" English, 1920):—

This can be slightly modified (*vide* Sand's "Electrochemistry and Electrochemical Analysis", Vol. III, p. 17),

which ionically would be represented as

From a comparative study of the generation efficiency of bichromate in alkaline, neutral and acid solutions with platinum anodes, Gross and Hickling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 325) suggest that perhaps the electrical energy changes bring about the formation of H_2O_2 thus :

and that the oxidation of chromium sulphate to chromic acid is due to chemical oxidation by H_2O_2 .

In view of the above divergent views it was considered essential to study the reaction in details so that the production of bichromate may be easily controlled. The investigation was divided into two parts, (i) elucidation of the effect of composition of the solution and (ii) elucidation of the effect of the composition of the electrode material.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Electrolyte.—To decide among various schemes of reactions suggested by the above workers, potentiometric method was adopted. The potential set up at an electrode depending on the concentration of ions of the reactants and those of the products. If, for example, the reaction runs according to the equation :

then the E.M.F. set up at an electrode dipped in a solution consisting of these four constituents in equilibrium will be given by the Nernst equation,

$$\begin{aligned} E - E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left\{ \frac{(\text{CrO}_4'')^2 \times (\text{H}')^{16}}{(\text{Cr}''')^2 \times (\text{H}_2\text{O})^8} \right\} \\ - E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \frac{2 \ln(\text{CrO}_4'') + 16 \ln(\text{H}')}{2 \ln(\text{Cr}''') + 8 \ln(\text{H}_2\text{O})} \\ - E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \left\{ 2 \ln(\text{CrO}_4'') + 16 \ln(\text{H}') - 2 \ln(\text{Cr}''') \right\} \end{aligned}$$

where $R = 8.31 \text{ Joules/1}^\circ$.

$T =$ Absolute temperature $= (273 + 28) = 301^\circ$.

$n =$ Valency of charge $= 6$.

$F = 1$ Faraday of electricity $= 96494$ coulombs.

E_0 is the normal potential of the solution—characteristic of the reaction—being that, which is set up when all the constituents of solution *i.e.*, the reactants and the products have unit activity or have concentration of 1 g. mol. per litre.

$$\begin{aligned} E - E_0 + 0.00998 [2 \log(\text{CrO}_4'') + 16 \log(\text{H}') - 2 \log(\text{Cr}''')] \\ = E_0 + 0.01 [2 \log(\text{CrO}_4'') + 16 \log(\text{H}') - 2 \log(\text{Cr}''')] \end{aligned}$$

Similarly for Sand's equation :

$$E = E_0 + 0.01[\log(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}) + 14\log(\text{H}^+) - 2\log(\text{Cr}^{3+})]$$

According to Gross and Hickling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 325) the electrolytic reaction is given by

applying the Nernst equation the E.M.F. set up should be given by the equation :

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \left\{ \ln \frac{(\text{H}_2\text{O}_2)}{(\text{OH}^+)^2} \right\}$$

i.e. $E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} [-2 \ln(\text{OH}^+)]$ (Since H_2O_2 decomposes as soon as formed, being used up for conversion of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ into H_2CrO_4 , its concentration at any moment is negligible, *i.e.*, until any $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ remains in solution).

$$= E_0 + \frac{0.059}{2} \left[(2\log 10^{-14} - 2\log(\text{H}^+)) \right]$$

$$= E_0 + \frac{0.059}{2} \left[(2 \times 14 + 2\log(\text{H}^+)) \right]$$

$$= E_0 + 0.826 + 0.059 \log(\text{H}^+).$$

Accessories.—Tinsley's vernier potentiometer depending on Poggendorf's compensation method of determining the E.M.F. was used during the course of the investigations.

In the present series of experiments mercurous sulphate—mercury electrode was used as the standard. The bridge connection to the test solution with the standard electrode was made slightly different from the prevailing types. This facilitated renewing the bridge solution $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (every time a new solution was tested) without much loss of time. This was considered essential as the chromium solution tended to creep up the bridge arms and gave unsteady results.

The E. M. F. of the accumulator was checked against standard cadmium cell before and after each reading with the test solution. The cadmium cell (made in the laboratory) used for this purpose was at intervals checked against standard cadmium cell supplied by Tinsleys.

FIG. 1

K = cell composed of (i) Anode of $\text{CrO}_4^{2-}/\text{Cr}^{3+}$, (ii) cathode of $\text{Hg}/\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4$. G = galvanometer.

A = accumulator and E = null point showing no deflections.

A platinum electrode dipping into the test solution was a spiral of bright platinum. This electrode and its shape was selected after a few preliminary experiments with (i) bright platinum, (ii) roughened platinum and (iii) platinised platinum and was found the best as it attained stability after a short time. This was used throughout the experiments in the first section of this investigation.

FIG. 2

Details of arrangement of cell K (vide Fig. 1)

Air-conditioning of the Apparatus.—An important factor towards getting reproducible results was the constancy of temperature of the whole apparatus, including the accumulator, the test solution, the bridge solution, standard electrode and the standard cell. A thermostat would enable only a few of these accessories to be kept at constant temperature leaving others, like the potentiometer and accumulator at room temperature, which fluctuated widely during the course of experiments.

It was decided therefore to carry out the series of experiments of Section I in an air-conditioned room, kept at a constant temperature of 82° . The effect of this conditioning was at once noticeable in the constancy and reproducibility of E.M.F. of standard cells and accumulator.

Standardisation of Mercurous Sulphate-Mercury Electrode.—Since this electrode *i.e.* mercury—mercurous sulphate—acid sulphuric electrode was used as a standard electrode throughout these investigations, its E.M.F. was determined against

normal calomel electrode. This value was also checked independently against hydrogen electrode. The values agree very well as shown.

	Determined E.M.F.	E.M.F. of calomel against Hydrogen.	E.M.F. of Hg ₂ SO ₄ against H ₂ .
(a) Hg Hg ₂ SO ₄ - Hg HgCl	+0.3585		
+	+0.3588		
-	+0.3588		
	+0.3585	+0.283	- +0.6415.

Calculated E.M.F. against H₂ electrode = -0.6415.

(b) Hg Hg ₂ SO ₄ - Hg H ₂ electrode	+0.642		
+	+0.643	normal	
	+0.642		
	+0.6423		
		E.M.F. directly determined	= +0.6423

Value of E.M.F. adopted during the investigation = +0.642 volts.

The following sixteen solutions were selected for determining their single electrode potentials. The solutions selected for test were made up of chromium sulphate, chromic acid and sulphuric acid and were made up so as to have a total of 0.68 g. mols. of chromium either as Cr⁺⁺⁺ or CrO₄^{''} in each solution under test. The exact proportions of these were

	I	II	III	IV
	g. mols. per litre	g. mols. per litre	g. mols. per litre	g. mols. per litre
CrO ₄ ^{''}	0.544	0.408	0.272	0.186
Cr ⁺⁺⁺	0.186	0.272	0.408	0.544

thus forming four different proportions of chromium. To each of these mixtures was added sulphuric acid so as to make the concentration of the solution with respect to sulphuric acid 4, 8, 12 and 16% (g./100 c.c.) thus making sixteen solutions. These concentrations of acid sulphuric besides giving ample variations of sulphuric acid for judging the effect of the reagent, also had the advantage that they corresponded with the acid concentrations of the electrolyte at four different stages of the regeneration process in our factory.

Chromic acid of 'Extra Pure' quality (Merck) was used for making a stock solution of chromic acid containing 1.36 g. mols of CrO₄^{''} per litre, by dissolving 100 g. of CrO₃ and making the solution to 735 c.c.

As chromium sulphate of good quality was not available, chromium sulphate solution was made by reducing 100 g. of the same chromic acid by SO₂ gas and ultimately adding a slight excess of freshly prepared strong solution of sulphurous acid to the hot solution. The complete reduction of chromate ion was

tested by mercurous nitrate solution. To remove any free H_2SO_3 it was evaporated slowly not above 70° . Above this temperature, changes in the constitutional formula of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ are likely to occur. The solution was then made to 1470 c.c. The concentration of Cr^{+++} ion in this stock solution was 0.68 g. mols. per litre.

A stock solution of acid sulphuric containing 800 g. per litre was made from Baker's 'Analysed' H_2SO_4 . This solution of H_2SO_4 was preferred as against concentrated H_2SO_4 , as it evolved very little heat when added to a mixture of chromic sulphate and chromic acid, which mixture was prepared about one hour before E.M.F. determination.

TABLE I

Stock solution of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 = 0.68$ g. mols./litre; that of $\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4 = 1.36$ g. mols./litre. and the stock solution of H_2SO_4 was 80 g./100 c.c. or 8 g. mols./litre.

Solution No	Stock H_2CrO_4 soln.	Stock $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ soln.	Stock H_2SO_4 soln.	Total vol.	CrO_4^{--} conc. per litre.	Cr^{+++} conc. per litre.	H_2SO_4 g./100c.c.
1	40 c.c.	20 c.c.	5 c.c.	100c.c.	0.544g. mol.	0.136 g. mol.	4
2	40	20	10	100	0.544	0.136	8
3	40	20	15	100	0.544	0.136	12
4	40	20	20	100	0.544	0.136	16
5	30	40	5	100	0.408	0.272	4
6	30	40	10	100	0.408	0.272	8
7	30	40	15	100	0.408	0.272	12
8	30	40	20	100	0.408	0.272	16
9	20	60	5	100	0.272	0.408	4
10	20	60	10	100	0.272	0.408	8
11	20	60	15	100	0.272	0.408	12
12	20	60	20	100	0.272	0.408	16
13	10	80	5	100	0.136	0.544	4
14	10	80	10	100	0.136	0.544	8

TABLE IA

Solution No.	Mean Pot. against std electrode.	Pot. calc. against Normal hydrogen electrode.
1	0.600 volt	1.242 volts
2	0.616	1.258
3	0.619	1.262
4	0.630	1.272

TABLE IB

Solution No.	Mean Pot. against std. electrode.	Pot calc. against N-hydrogen electrode.
5	0.604 volt	1.246 volts
6	0.605	1.247
7	0.618	1.250
8	0.629	1.271

TABLE IC

9	0.601	1.243
10	0.603	1.245
11	0.618	1.260
12	0.628	1.270

TABLE ID

13	0.564	1.206
14	0.589	1.231
15*		
16*		

In Tables IA, IB, IC, and ID are summarised the results of actual experiments carried out with solutions of different composition (These compositions are explained against corresponding numbers of solutions in the preceding table).

TABLE II A

Values for the expression $\frac{RT}{NF} [2\ln(\text{CrO}_4'') - 16\ln(\text{H}^+) - 2\ln(\text{Cr}^{\dots})]$

being the concentration correction to E .

(Values according to equation I)

Solution No.	Conc. of CrO_4'' (g. mols. per litre)	Conc. of Cr^{\dots}	H_2SO_4 (g./100 c.c.)	H^+ conc. from H_2CrO_4^*	H^+ conc. from $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4^{**}$	Value of $\frac{RT}{NF}$ (etc.)
1	0.544	0.136	4	1.088	0.44	+0.041
2	0.544	0.136	8	1.088	0.81	+0.056
3	0.544	0.136	12	1.088	1.147	+0.067
4	0.544	0.136	16	1.088	1.385	+0.075
5	0.408	0.272	4	0.816	0.44	+0.019
6	0.408	0.272	8	0.816	0.81	+0.037
7	0.408	0.272	12	0.816	1.147	+0.050
8	0.408	0.272	16	0.816	1.385	+0.058
9	0.272	0.408	4	0.544	0.44	-0.005
10	0.272	0.408	8	0.544	0.81	+0.017
11	0.272	0.408	12	0.544	1.147	+0.033
12	0.272	0.408	16	0.544	1.385	+0.042
13	0.136	0.544	4	0.272	0.44	-0.036
14	0.136	0.544	8	0.272	0.81	-0.006

* For lack of data complete ionisation assumed for simplicity.

** On the basis of actual ionisation data.

TABLE II B

Values of the expression $\frac{RT}{NF} (\ln(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7') + 14\ln(\text{H}^+) - 2\ln(\text{Cr}^{\dots}))$

being the concentration correction to E .

(According to equation II)

Soln. No.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7'$ conc. in g. mols./litre.	Cr^{\dots} conc. in g. mols./litre.	H_2SO_4 g./100 c.c.	Hydrogen H_2CrO_7^*	ion conc. from $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4^{**}$	Value of $\frac{RT}{NF}$ (etc.)
1	0.272	0.136	4	0.544	0.44	+0.011
2	0.272	0.136	8	0.544	0.81	+0.028
3	0.272	0.136	12	0.544	1.147	+0.034
4	0.272	0.136	16	0.544	1.385	+0.041
5	0.204	0.272	4	0.408	0.44	+0.015
6	0.204	0.272	8	0.408	0.81	+0.018
7	0.204	0.272	12	0.408	1.147	+0.034
8	0.204	0.272	16	0.408	1.385	+0.041
9	0.136	0.408	4	0.272	0.44	+0.0025
10	0.136	0.408	8	0.272	0.81	+0.009
11	0.136	0.408	12	0.272	1.147	+0.025
12	0.136	0.408	16	0.272	1.385	+0.036
13	0.068	0.544	4	0.136	0.44	-0.04
14	0.068	0.544	8	0.136	0.81	+0.006

* For lack of data complete ionisation assumed for simplicity.

** On the basis of actual ionisation data.

TABLE IIc

Corrections of $\frac{RT}{NF} [-2 \ln(\text{OH}')]$ to be applied to E for obtaining E_0

according to equation III derived from Glasstone and Hickling's assumption.

Soln. No.	H ⁺ conc. from H ₂ CrO ₄	H ⁺ conc. from H ₂ SO ₄	Total H ⁺ ion conc.	Correction. (0.826 + 0.059 log. H ⁺)
1	0.544	0.44	0.984	0.826
2	0.544	0.81	1.354	0.834
3	0.544	1.147	1.691	0.839
4	0.544	1.385	1.929	0.843
5	0.408	0.44	0.848	0.820
6	0.408	0.81	1.218	0.831
7	0.408	1.147	1.555	0.837
8	0.408	1.385	1.793	0.841
9	0.272	0.44	0.712	0.815
10	0.272	0.81	1.082	0.828
11	0.272	1.147	1.419	0.835
12	0.272	1.385	1.657	0.839
13	0.136	0.44	0.576	0.812
14	0.136	0.81	0.946	0.823

Conc. in g. mols per litre.

TABLE III

Calculated values of E
(On the hydrogen scale.)

Soln. No.	Eqn. I.	Eqn. II.	Eqn. III.	Soln. No.	Eqn. I.	Eqn. II.	Eqn. III.
1	1.200 volts	1.231 volts.	0.416 volt.	8	1.213 volts	1.230 volts	0.430 volt
2	1.202	1.230	0.424	9	1.239	1.241	0.428
3	1.194	1.227	0.422	10	1.228	1.235	0.417
4	1.197	1.231	0.429	11	1.227	1.235	0.425
5	1.227	1.231	0.416	12	1.229	1.233	0.431
6	1.210	1.229	0.416	13	1.242	1.246	0.394
7	1.210	1.226	0.423	14	1.237	1.225	0.408
				Mean	1.212	1.232	0.420

Comparison of the values of E_0 (Table III) as obtained by three equations shows great divergencies between values obtained by equation I and II on the one hand and those obtained by equation III on the other.

A direct determinations of E_0 value by taking equal concentrations of CrO_4^{2-} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and Cr^{+++} and unit concentration of H^+ ions (as detailed in Table IV) were made. Under these conditions of concentration, the expressions $\frac{RT}{NF}$ (etc.) in equations I and II reduce to 0 and the value of E obtained equals E_0 .

TABLE IV

Direct value of E_0 .

Conc. of CrO_4^{2-} g. mols/litre.	Conc. of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ g. mols/litre.	Conc. of Cr^{+++} g. mols/litre.	Total H ⁺ conc. g. mols/litre.	Value of E i.e. E_0
0.136	—	0.136	1	1.211
—	0.136	0.136	1	1.216
0.34	—	0.340	1	1.222
—	0.34	0.340	1	1.241
0.408	—	0.408	1	1.218

These values show a great divergence from E_0 value 0.420 calculated by equation III (on the assumption of Gross and Hickling regarding the mechanism of reaction). On the other hand they agree more closely with the values of E_0 calculated by equations I and II and are of the same order. Gross and Hickling

assumptions of the course of electrolytic oxidation seem to have not much justification at least in acid solutions. It is also to be noted that the equation derived from reaction mechanism of these authors does not allow for any change in the value of E with concentration of Cr^{+++} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ or CrO_4^{--} ions.

The values of E_0 obtained from equations I and II above (Table III) are reasonably constant and are of the same order of magnitude to those obtained experimentally. Further, the equations also account for the observed facts that the E.M.F. varies with the concentrations of Cr^{+++} and CrO_4^{--} or $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ and H^+ . The values obtained from equation I vary slightly more among themselves and from the mean 1.212 volts than those obtained from equation II of which the mean value is 1.232 volts. From these considerations, the mechanism of electrolytic oxidation should be well represented by equation II in which the bichromate and not chromate ions are supposed to be the product of oxidation. It is well known that in the presence of hydrogen ions the balanced reaction $2\text{CrO}_4^{--} \xrightleftharpoons[\text{-H}^+]{\text{+H}^+} \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ is largely shifted towards high concentration of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ in preference to CrO_4^{--} ions. The solutions tested are all highly acidic and it can be assumed that $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ changes to $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.

In the calculation of E_0 , the simplifying assumption is made that Cr^{+++} in chromium sulphate and CrO_4^{--} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ in H_2CrO_4 and $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ are all completely ionised at dilutions under investigation. This simple assumption cannot hold good particularly for such salt as $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ which, as is well known, exhibits great tendency towards formation of not easily ionised, hydrated and sulphated complexes.

The chromic acid, analogous to sulphuric acid, is far from being completely ionised. Thus the simplifying assumption made, naturally renders the E_0 value, obtained (i) directly (Table IV) and (ii) those calculated from the measured E.M.F. values of solution in which the concentration of H^+ ion is not unit and in which CrO_4^{--} and Cr^{+++} are not equal (Table III), slightly different from their true value.

Further work is in progress to determine the true extent of ionisation of solutions of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and H_2CrO_4 and H_2SO_4 in presence of all the three dilutions in question, so as to get an idea of Cr^{+++} , CrO_4^{--} or $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ ions present in them.

CONCLUSION

The process of oxidation can therefore be said to be represented by

It is not necessary to enunciate a new reaction or equation to bring out the fact that the reaction takes place best in alkaline solution. This is brought out also by equation (II) because in this equation also the higher the H^+ ion value, the greater is the tendency to proceed to the left side of equation or reducing. The equation (II) is favoured also by the fact that it allows for change of E with concentration of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ and Cr^{+++} as found experimentally.